

The Influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Commitment at PT. Persada Technical Media

Riswan Sidik¹, Abdi Sugiarto²

Magister Manajemen, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: riswansidik73@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of organizational climate on employee commitment at PT. Media Teknik Persada. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all employees with a total of 67 people taken using proportional sampling. The research results show that organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment. This is shown by the T-count value of T-count of 8.633 > t table 1.66864, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if organizational climate is increased by 1 unit, employee commitment will increase by 0.311 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.527 or 52.70%, which indicates that organizational climate has a low influence on employee commitment, while the remaining 47.30% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee work at PT. Media Teknik Persada. This identifies that improvements in the organizational climate can contribute to increased employee commitment.

Keywords: organizational climate; employee commitment

INTRODUCTION

Modern organizations are increasingly realizing the importance of understanding the factors that influence employee performance and engagement. One key factor that has become a major focus in this context is organizational climate. Organizational climate reflects the atmosphere, norms, values and culture that exist within an organization. The existence of a conducive organizational climate can influence various aspects of employees, including their commitment to the organization where they work (Hartanti, 2024).

Organizational climate is an important factor in supporting the performance of an organization, because indirectly a conducive organizational climate will trigger work enthusiasm, job satisfaction and support efforts to improve employee performance (Lineker et al., 2016). Every organization will have a different work climate. The diversity of jobs designed within the organization, or the nature of the individuals present will reflect these differences.

Even though organizational climate has been recognized as being able to support the performance of an organization, the understanding of this climate is still too general. This raises the need for a more comprehensive understanding, especially in the context of job diversity and the nature of individuals in organizations (Idrus, 2006). In addition, although it is known that a conducive organizational climate can influence various aspects of employees, it is still unclear how specifically the organizational climate contributes to improving employee performance.

Based on the results of initial observations, the phenomenon that occurred at PT. Media Teknik Persada obtained information that several employees showed a low level of commitment, which can be related to their perception of the organizational climate. A supportive organizational climate, including a conducive work environment and good working conditions, contributes to increased job satisfaction and employee commitment. Conversely, an organizational climate that is less supportive can cause employees to feel dissatisfied and less motivated.

These observations indicate that organizational climate plays an important role in shaping employee commitment. To understand a clearer relationship between organizational climate and employee commitment at PT. Media Teknik Persada, further analysis is needed. This analysis will help identify specific aspects of the organizational climate that need to be improved to increase employee commitment and motivation and create a more positive and productive work environment.

This research refers to the results of research (Rustini & Muslichah, 2022) which states that organizational climate has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. Employee commitment is a situation where employees decide to take sides, together realizing the vision and mission and the desire to remain as employees in a particular company. (Robbins, Stephen P. and Mary Coulter, 2016). Meanwhile (Kusumaputri, 2015) explains that employee commitment is a force that makes a person bound to complete work that is the company's goal. Best stated that when someone is able to commit to carrying out all the work and behave specifically based on the seriousness of good morals rather than just benefiting themselves.

In this study, to measure work commitment, researchers refer to the opinion expressed by (Robbins, Stephen P. and Mary Coulter, 2016) consisting of:

1. The Will to Survive

It reflects the level of emotion involved in an individual's involvement with the organization they work for. Individuals who have a desire to stay tend to have positive feelings toward the organization, feel emotionally connected, and are more likely to commit to staying.

2. Attachment to the Organization

This attachment is related to social norms and individual moral feelings towards the organization. Individuals who have normative attachments tend to feel that they have a moral obligation to remain committed to the organization, regardless of their personal interests.

3. Commitment Based on Calculations

It deals with an individual's assessment of the costs and benefits associated with staying in the organization. Individuals with calculation-based commitment tend to stay because they feel that the costs of leaving the organization are higher than the benefits.

Many factors can influence employee commitment. This research is limited to organizational climate factors. Organizational climate is the quality of the internal environment that is relatively long-lasting based on employee acceptance. Organizational

climate is based on employee perceptions which influence the atmosphere of the internal environment, which plays an important role in achieving organizational success (Hartanti, 2024). Meanwhile (Pranata & Utama, 2018) states that organizational climate is the perception of organizational members (individually or in groups) and they are in constant contact with the organization regarding what exists or happens in the organization's internal environment on a regular basis, which influences the attitudes and behavior of the organization which then determines performance. organization.

According to the Intifada in (Pranata & Utama, 2018) states that there are seven indicators of organizational climate, namely as follows:

1) Leadership.

The behavior or interaction of a leader in coordinating and moving subordinates to achieve organizational goals.

2) Trust.

There is an attitude of mutual trust between employees and leaders while continuing to develop and maintain relationships full of confidence and trust.

3) Joint decision making or support.

Employees at all levels of the organization must be invited to communicate and consult on all issues in all organizational policies that are relevant to their position and participate in decision making and goal setting.

4) Honesty.

A general atmosphere filled with honesty and candor that characterizes relationships between employees within the organization, where employees are able to say what is on their minds

5) Communication.

Employees have the right to know information related to their duties and authority.

6) Flexibility or autonomy.

Employees have autonomy in their own work tasks, and have the power to accept or guess suggestions with an open mind. This means that employees have the freedom to express their opinions.

7) Occupational risk.

Employees are aware of the risks of work and remain committed and loyal to the company.

The aim of this research is to investigate the influence of organizational climate on employee commitment at PT. Media Teknik Persada. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image i

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at PT. Media Teknik Persada which is located at Jl. Villa Gading Mas I No.3, Harjosari II, Medan Amplas District, Medan City. The time this research was carried out was from March to May 2024. The population in this study was the entire number of employees at PT. Media Teknik Persada with a total of 67 employees with the following details:

Table 1. Population Details at PT. Media Teknik Persada

No.	Division	Number of people)
1.	Electrical	47
2.	Transformation	10
3.	Marketing	6
4.	HRD and Finance	4
Amount		67

Source: PT. Media Teknik Persada

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 67 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee commitment

X = Organizational climate

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to

measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely organizational climate (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee commitment (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

A. Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Organizational climate	67	3.60	5.00	4.3910	.45718
Employee commitment	67	3.00	5.00	4.3134	.45490
Valid N (listwise)	67				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the organizational climate and employee commitment at PT. Media Teknik Persada is above average, with mean scores of 4,391 and 4,313 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.457 for organizational climate and 0.454 for employee commitment), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of these two variables.

B. Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Organizational Climate Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.810 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.919 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

X3	0.864 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.865 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X5	0.888 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X6	0.788 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X7	0.829 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the organizational climate variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.2404 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the organizational climate variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Employee Commitment Variable Validity Test Results (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.881 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.885 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.870 > 0.2404	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee commitment variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2404 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee commitment variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Organizational climate	0.935	7
Employee commitment	0.852	3

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the organizational climate and employee commitment variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

C. Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3,374	1,114		3,029	,004
Organizational climate	,311	,036	,731	8,633	,000

Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 3.374 + 0.311X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 3.374 means that if there is no organizational climate, then there is employee commitment of 3.374 points. The organizational climate regression coefficient is 0.311, meaning that organizational climate influences an increase in employee commitment of 0.311 for every 1 point increase

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.731a	,534	,527	.93418

Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Climate

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.527 or 52.70%, which means that organizational climate has a moderate influence on employee commitment, while the remaining 47.30% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of organizational climate on employee commitment at PT. Media Teknik Persada

Ha: There is an influence of organizational climate on employee commitment at PT. Media Teknik Persada

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3,374	1,114		3,029	,004
Organizational climate	.311	,036	,731	8,633	,000

Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 8.633 > t table 1.66864, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between organizational climate on employee commitment to PT. Persada Engineering Media.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of organizational climate on employee commitment, these findings are in line with research results (Kustianto & Abidin Iskhak, 2015) and (Cahyadi & Utama, 2018) which show that organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment.

These findings have important implications for PT. Media Teknik Persada, shows that a positive organizational climate plays a significant role in increasing employee commitment. To achieve this, companies need to create and maintain a supportive work environment, comfortable working conditions, and transparent and fair policies. In addition, providing training programs and clear career paths, as well as increasing management involvement in understanding employee needs, is critical. Appropriate performance rewards and incentives, effective communication, and regular feedback will also strengthen employee motivation and commitment. With these steps, companies can improve their organizational climate, increase employee satisfaction and motivation, and drive productivity and long-term success.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. Hypothesis test results show that organizational climate has a positive effect on employee commitment. This can be seen from the T-count value of 8.633 > t table 1.66864, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This regression coefficient shows that if organizational climate is increased by 1 unit, then the change in employee commitment as seen from the Y value will increase by 0.311 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially the organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at PT. Persada Engineering Media.

2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.527 or 52.70%, which means that organizational climate has a moderate influence on employee commitment, while the remaining 47.30% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the findings, discussion and conclusions from this research, several things can be suggested to the institution, namely the PT Office. Media Teknik Persada is as follows:

1. PT. Media Teknik Persada should focus on improving the organizational climate through creating a more conducive work environment, transparency in policies, and providing management support. These steps may include improving work facilities, developing fair policies, and actively involving management in daily interactions with employees.
2. Companies need to provide ongoing training and development programs as well as clear career paths for employees. This will not only improve employees' skills and competencies, but can also increase their motivation and commitment to the company. In addition, providing appropriate rewards and incentives based on employee performance will encourage them to be more committed and contribute to the company's success.

REFERENCES

- Ahluwalia, L., & Puji, K. (2020). The Influence of Empowering Leadership on Homework Performance and Balance during the Covid-19 Pandemic.
- Cahyadi, MK, & Utama, IWM (2018). The Influence of Organizational Climate on Organizational Commitment and Retention of Contract Employees in BAPPEDA R&D Bali Province. *Udayana University Management E-Journal*, 7(10), 5508. <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJMUNUD.2018.v07.i10.p11>
- Djaluputro, S., & Andrias, MS (2023). Analysis of Leadership Style in Employee Engagement at PT. DMI: Qualitative Case Study. *Ocean Journal of Economics and Business*, 14(3), 514–529. <https://doi.org/10.33059/jseb.v14i3.8230>
- Ghozali, I. (2016). *Multivariate Analysis Applications with the IBM SPSS 23 Program* (Edition 8). Printing VII. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- Hartanti, R. (2024). The Relationship Between Organizational Climate and Organizational Commitment in PT Employees. *Harapan Jaya Sentosa. . . Characters*, 11.
- Kuncooro, Munajad. (2013). *Research Methods for Business and Economics*. Edition 4. Erlangga.
- Kustianto, F., & Abidin Iskhak, A. (2015). The Influence of Organizational Climate on Employee Commitment with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at PT. Garam (Persero). *MAGISTRA Management Science Journal*. <https://jurnal.narotama.ac.id/index.php/magistra/article/view/24>
- Kusumaputri. (2015). *Commitment to Organizational Change*. Deepublish.

- Pranata, IGN, & Utama, IWM (2018). The Influence of Organizational Climate on Turnover Intention with Job Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable. *Udayana University Management E-Journal*, 8(1), 526. <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJMUNUD.2019.v08.i01.p19>
- Robbins, Stephen P. and Mary Coulter. (2016). *Management*, Volume 1 Edition 13, Translation: Bob Sabran and Devri Bardani P. Erlangga.
- Rustini, T., & Muslichah, M. (2022). The Influence of Organizational Climate on Job Satisfaction with Organizational Commitment as a Mediating Variable. *NUSANTARA JOURNAL OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT APPLICATIONS*, 7(1), 162–173. <https://doi.org/10.29407/nusamba.v7i1.14826>
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods*. CV. Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methodologies and R&D*. Alfabeta.